

INTELLIGENT DEVICES FOR DIAGNOSTICS AND THERAPY WITH PULSED CURRENT

AYNUR Jabiyeva J.¹, ANAKHANIM Mutallimova S².

^{1, 2} Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Department of Instrumentation Engineering, Azerbaijan,
Baku, str . 20, AZE 1010

¹ Dosent , <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0336-8586> , Aynur.Jabiyeva@outlook.com , 050-344-99-54, AZE 1010

² Dosent , <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-8327-192X> , Anaxanim.mutallimova@asoiiu.edu.az , 050-440-22-31, AZE 1009

Abstract .

Currently, there are a large number of different methods of separate treatment of individual diseases. Despite the diversity of drugs and methods, the use of each of them separately is often aimed at the links of pathogenesis of one disease, which to a certain extent explains their insufficient effectiveness in combined pathology. Existing drug treatment methods are insufficiently effective in the presence of combined pathology, often have many side effects, in some cases contribute to the exacerbation of chronic diseases and allergization of the body. Electric current therapy is actively used in modern medical practice. It is used for therapeutic and preventive purposes, as well as for rehabilitation after injuries and illnesses. This type of physiotherapy also includes therapeutic effects on the body using electromagnetic fields that have different parameters. Devices that supply current in continuous or pulsed mode are used for treatment.

Keywords

Intelligent devices, electromagnetic radiation, pulsed fields, pulsed current, electrodes for electrodiagnostics.

Intellektual cihazlar, elektromaqnit şüalanma, impulsu sahələr, impuls cərəyanı, elektrodiagnostika üçün elektrodlar.

Интеллектуальные устройства, электромагнитное излучение, импульсные поля, импульсный ток, электроды для электродиагностики.

1.INTRODUCTION

In recent years, methods have been developed in restorative medicine based on the generation and transmission of very low-power signals to the body, which do not cause noticeable changes in tissue temperature, but determine information flows that specifically regulate the body's functions. Such factors include electromagnetic fields.

This article shows that the specificity of the body's reactions is most clearly manifested when using low-intensity factors of electromagnetic nature, the energy of which is insufficient to heat tissues and change their functions. The introduced energy serves as a kind of "trigger" for the redistribution of the free energy of cells and tissues, significantly changing their metabolism and functional properties, i.e. it has an informational effect [10]. The choice of the mode of exposure to electromagnetic radiation is due to the fact that its result depends on the synchronization of the oscillatory process of the acting external factor and the normal rhythm of functioning of the corresponding system of the human body

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

with optimal energy parameters of this factor, time and periodicity of its exposure [12].

Figure 1. Artificial intelligence enhanced sensors biomedical platform

Therapy using a pulsed low-frequency electromagnetic field emerged in the middle of the last century and made it possible to simultaneously exert polyfactorial influence on various biological systems of the body, which determined a unique physiotherapeutic therapeutic effect [12]. With non-contact exposure, the therapeutic effect of a pulsed low-frequency electromagnetic field is realized through the optic, thalamo- and hypothalamic-pituitary system due to the regulation of subcortical-cortical bioelectric processes, the exchange of neurotransmitters, endorphin and immune systems, hormonal activity of the endocrine glands, improvement of neurodynamics, as a result of which microcirculation in tissues, general and peripheral circulation, and blood rheology are normalized [1, 3, 4]. A pulsed low-frequency electromagnetic field also has an analgesic, sedative and anti-inflammatory effect [5, 13].

2.PROBLEM STATEMENT AND PURPOSE OF WORK

Intelligent data of experimental morphological studies convincingly show that the effect of a pulsed low-frequency electromagnetic field with a daily changing pulse repetition rate on the head area creates optimal conditions for organotypic regeneration of the connective tissue of the sclera. The similarity of submicroscopic changes in organelles during the response reaction of the formation of adaptation processes has been established: the ultrastructural morphology reflects the process of enhanced functioning of all cells of the fibroblastic differon. The general and key process in the cellular response is the formation of a connective tissue regenerate around the cellular structures, organ-specific for a given tissue structure. Differences in subpopulation rearrangements within the fibroblast differon have also been noted. Thus, for the sclera of healthy eyes, the use of information-wave technology creates conditions for the presence

**2024 International Conference on Artificial intelligence: from theory to practice,
17-18 september 2024, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan**

of cells with a response reaction of "calm" activation and a reaction of increased activation of biosynthetic processes, with the presence of an insignificant number of cellular forms with structureless zones.

The data of experimental morphological studies allowed to substantiate and develop a new technology for the treatment of progressive myopia, combined with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, in the form of transcranial exposure to a pulsed low-frequency electromagnetic field generated by an intelligent device .

The advantage of the proposed treatment technology is the creation of optimal conditions for organotypic regeneration of the connective tissue of the sclera, activation of synthetic processes in fibrocytes and fibroblasts and the formation of a regenerate of the collagen network, not involved in the inflammatory process, which contributes to an increase in the effectiveness of the treatment of progressive myopia, combined with extraocular pathology, united by the syndrome of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia. Study of problem. Indications for use intelligent medical technology. General contraindications to physiotherapeutic procedures, in particular, a pathological process in he acute stage, a tendency to bleeding, individual intolerance to this physical factor.

The main features of the electromagnetic field in the therapy zone: the electric field at any given time has the structure of an electrostatic dipole field, retains traces of stationarity and is called a quasi-stationary electrostatic field. Medical technology consists of several stages and includes examination and a method of transcranial exposure to a pulsed low-frequency electromagnetic field using an intelligent device against the background of conservative therapy for chronic pathology.

Electric current, constant in direction and unchanging in magnitude, causes certain physical and chemical processes in the body tissues, which are based on a change in the concentration of ions in the tissue elements. These processes determine the therapeutic effect of the current. However, there are a number of phenomena or reactions of the body that occur with current. For example, instantaneous switching on or off of direct current causes irritation of the elements of the nervous system, which can be especially clearly observed when affecting the peripheral neuromuscular apparatus, the reaction of which is manifested by the contraction of the corresponding muscles. Therefore, one of the very common means of influencing the nervous system in electrotherapy is the impact of impulses, or pulses, of direct current.

The main characteristics of the pulse current (which largely determine its physiological effect) are: a) the pulse repetition frequency, or the period of the pulse current; b) the duration of each pulse, or the so-called duty cycle of the current, equal to the ratio of the period to the duration of the pulse; c) the shape of the pulse, especially the steepness of the leading edge.

In the picture 2 shows a graph of a rectangular pulse current. If we denote the pulse repetition frequency as f Hz, then the period of the pulse current will be $T = 1/f$ sec. If the pulse duration is equal to t sec, then the pause after each pulse will be $t_0 = T - t$ sec and the duty cycle: $S = T/t$.

The duty cycle (with a rectangular pulse shape) also determines the relationship between the average and amplitude values of voltage U or current I ;

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

Figure 2. The relationship between the pulse duration and the period in the pulse current

Average voltage value $U_{cp} = U_a t / T = U_a / S$.

Average value of current $I_{cp} = I_a t / T = I_a / S$,

U_a And I_a - amplitude voltage and current. Conversely,

$U_a = S U_{cp}$ And $I_a = S I_{cp}$.

Thus, the average value of the pulse voltage or current is equal to the amplitude value divided by the duty cycle. Or, conversely, the amplitude value of the voltage or current is equal to the average multiplied by the duty cycle.

It is important to take this into account in connection with the fact that the irritating effect of a pulsed current depends mainly on the amplitude value of the current and the duration of the pulse. The average value of the current is much less characteristic in this respect. At the same time, it is the average value of the current that is measured by the most common magnetoelectric devices in practice; measuring the amplitude value with sufficiently short pulses requires the use of special measuring circuits.

Modern electronic technology makes it possible to obtain current pulses whose parameters vary within the widest ranges, measured, for example, by frequency from units to millions of hertz; by duration from seconds to microseconds; by shape, pulses can also vary within wide limits, up to the possibility of reproducing any pulse shape written on paper.

In the picture 3 shows graphs of pulse current of various shapes, mainly used in medical practice:

a) faradic current in its classical form, or current from an induction coil;

2024 International Conference on Artificial intelligence: from theory to practice, 17-18 september 2024, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Figure 3. Pulse currents of various nature

- b) tetanizing current, which is short-term triangular-shaped pulses reproducing the opening pulses of faradic current;
- c) capacitor discharges with an exponentially decaying trailing edge ;
- d) rectangular pulses;
- d) exponentially increasing pulses;
- c) exponentially increasing and decreasing pulses.

When using pulsed current to affect the tissues of the body, it should be taken into account that the electrical conductivity of the latter is not purely ohmic, but also has a capacitive component. In its most general form, the equivalent electrical circuit of the circuit located between the electrodes when exposed to direct or pulsed current, it can be represented as several series-connected resistances, each of which is shunted by a capacitor (Figure 4).

In this circuit R_0 and C_0 denote the resistance and capacitance of electrodes, pads, and the layer of skin and subcutaneous tissue, in which capacitive elements have a relatively large value, and R and C denote the resistance and capacitance of deeper tissues of the body, in which capacitance has a smaller value.

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

Figure 4. Equivalent electrical circuit for body tissues

In the first approximation, for a rectangular pulse current with an insignificant value of current used in practice, the order of magnitude for R is taken 1000-2000 ohms, C 0.03-0.05 μF , R 500-1000 ohms and C 0.01-0.02 μF .

The consequence of the capacitive properties of tissues is that the shape of the current pulses passing through them differs somewhat from the shape of the applied voltage pulses. This circumstance must be taken into account in precise studies. In ordinary medical or diagnostic practice, it is of little importance. As an example, Figure 5 shows a schematic shape of current pulses I , obtained when the tissues of the body are exposed to voltage pulses U of a rectangular shape.

Determination of the functional or anatomical state of nerve trunks or muscles using stimulation with electric current (electrodiagnostics). Electrodiagnostics compares the form of electrical stimulation with the nature of the response, mainly in the form of muscle contraction.

In accordance with the nature of electrical stimulation, the methods of electrodiagnostics also differ. The simplest of them is the so-called class method, in which the nature of contraction of the affected muscles is compared with stimulation by constant and tetanizing (Figure 5, b) current. Despite the existence of significantly more advanced methods, the "classical method" retains its significance as the simplest, fastest, not requiring complex equipment and at the same time quite reliable.

2024 International Conference on Artificial intelligence: from theory to practice, 17-18 september 2024, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Figure 5. Artificial intelligence enhanced sensors - enabling technologies to next-generation healthcare and biomedical platform

Electrodiagnostic method.

The most widespread and advanced method is electrodiagnostics using single rectangular pulses (Fig. 3 , g). The method is based on the fact that the irritating effect of relatively short-term (small doses of a second) current pulses depends on their duration. This dependence is expressed by the so-called electrical excitability curve, which gives the relationship between the magnitude of the current i_n , causing the threshold (i.e. the least noticeable) irritation reaction, and the duration of Δa single current pulse. This curve is also called the "strength - duration" curve. An approximate character of the curve is shown in the figure 6.

Figure 6. An approximate character of the curve

An approximate character of the curve on the dependence of the irritating effect of single current pulses on their duration, in which two characteristic parameters of the electrical excitability curve are determined. The first is called the rheobase R (Figure 5) and represents the magnitude of the threshold stimulation current for any given pulse duration. The second is called chronaxie σ and represents the duration of the pulse corresponding to the threshold stimulation equal to twice the rheobase. Chronaximetry is a simpler study than determining the strength - duration curve and was once performed using capacitor discharges. The corresponding apparatus was called a " capacitor chronaximeter . "

In addition to stimulation by single impulses, stimulation by impulses repeating with a certain

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən praktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

frequency ("frequency" stimulation) is also used in electrodiagnostics. In this case, a special value is determined, called "lability" and characterizing the ability of tissue or organ to perceive a particular stimulation rhythm. During the study, a connection is established between the nature of muscle contraction and the frequency of electrical stimulation. Electrodiagnostics is carried out using rectangular impulses, the frequency of which varies within very wide limits.

There are methods of electrodiagnostics, in which a relationship is established between the nature of muscle contraction and the shape of current pulses, especially the steepness of the leading edge. In this case, triangular or exponential pulses are used (Figure 3, d) forms.

3.RESULT

Finally , there are more complex methods for studying electrical excitability, in which all three main parameters of electrical impulses are changed simultaneously or in certain combinations: duration , frequency and shape.

Electrical stimulation of nerve trunks and muscles is used as a method of treating neuromuscular lesions, which aims to support the vital activity of muscles through artificial contraction when their innervation is impaired. This method is called electrical stimulation (the old name is electrogymnastics). For In electrostimulation, the same methods of electrical stimulation are used as for electrodiagnostics. Usually, electrodiagnostics are carried out first, which allows one to determine the functional state of the nervous - muscular apparatus and, in connection with this, to establish the most favorable parameters for influencing it with electrical stimulation . Then, using a current with the parameters thus established, muscle stimulation is performed.

In both electrodiagnostics and electrostimulation, electrical stimulation is applied to the object using two electrodes: active and inactive. The active electrode has a small area (less than 1 cm^2) and is therefore called a point electrode. The inactive electrode has the shape of a plate of considerable area. This method of action is called unipolar. The electrode in this case (Figure 7, a) has the shape of a curved rod *1* with a thickening at the end, inserted into the handle 4. The handle has a push-button switch 2-3, allowing the examiner to arbitrarily turn the current circuit on and off. The end of the electrode is covered with a cloth, which is moistened with warm physiological solution or water during the procedure. The inactive electrode is also supplied with a moistened pad.

Figure 7. Electrodes for electrodiagnostics
a - single-pole, b - double-pole

In the case of unipolar electrical stimulation, either a similar point electrode is used, but without a breaker, or a small lead plate covered with fabric is placed on the irritated point and bandaged with a rubber bandage.

Both in electrodiagnostics and especially in electrostimulation, a bipolar stimulation method is often used. The electrode for electrodiagnostics is shown in Figure 6 and consists of two curved rods (branches) 1 with a thickening at the end (like a single-pole electrode), fixed in a common handle 3. The electrode branches are sliding and can be installed at any necessary distance. Wires from the device are connected to both branches. The electrode handle is equipped with a breaker 2 in the circuit of one wire.

In bipolar stimulation, both electrodes are active and are located at two points: either at the ends of the muscle being examined or along a section of the nerve trunk. In bipolar electrical stimulation, two small lead plates covered with fabric are used, which are located at the ends of the corresponding muscle (or group of muscles) and are bandaged with an elastic bandage.

During electrical stimulation of muscles, electrical stimulation must be delivered to the muscle rhythmically with pauses between the impulses to provide the necessary muscle rest between contractions. This requires the installation of a device in the apparatus for electrical stimulation of muscles for rhythmic delivery of current to the patient's electrodes.

In cases where the patient retains the ability to perform at least minor active movement with the affected muscles, so-called active stimulation is used. Active stimulation consists of the electrical stimulation being combined in time with the patient's attempt to perform active movement. In this case, electrical stimulation serves as a means of enhancing muscle contraction and, thus, promoting a more complete restoration of the impaired function. The pulse current is switched on in separate bursts using a special foot or hand modulator.

The so-called diadynamic therapy also belongs to the methods of treatment with pulsed currents of various types.

In this case, a pulsed current of a slightly modified sinusoidal shape is used, modulated in the form of pulses of varying duration, which is supplied to the area of the body to be affected by means of electrodes similar to those used in galvanization. Diadynamic currents are used to eliminate pain and trophic disorders in tissues.

Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans, 17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan

Conclusion

Thus, the developed intelligent technology for treating connective tissue allows improving immediate and remote results: The method is simple to perform, available for mass treatment, non-invasive, painless, does not require expensive equipment and special preparation of the patient for the procedures, its use is possible both in school and outpatient settings, and in hospitals. The shape and frequency of impulses of pulsed electrotherapy are similar to the characteristics of signals that spread through the peripheral nervous system to the brain. Due to this, this type of electrotherapy blocks pain in the inflammatory focus better than other procedures. Electrotherapy has a highly effective and safe therapeutic effect on the body. In the absence of contraindications for treatment with electrical exposure, it is possible to get rid of a number of symptoms in chronic diseases.

References

1. Zheng, W.; Liu, M.; Liu, C.; Wang, D.; Li, K. Recent Advances in Sensor Technology for Healthcare and Canali, S.; Schiaffonati, V.; Aliverti, A. Challenges and recommendations for wearable devices in digital health: Data quality, interoperability, health equity, fairness. *PLoS Digit. Health* **2022** , 1 , e0000104.
2. Li, Y.; Liu, C.; Zou, H.; Che, L.; Sun, P.; Yan, J.; Liu, W.; Xu, Z.; Yang, W.; Dong, L.; et al. Integrated wearable smart sensor system for real-time multi-parameter respiration health monitoring. *Cell Rep. Phys. Sci.* **2023** , 4 , 101191.]
3. Vijayan, V.; Connolly, JP; Condell, J.; McKelvey, N.; Gardiner, P. Review of Wearable Devices and Data Collection Considerations for Connected Health. *Sensors* **2021** , 21 , 5589.
4. Al-Kahtani, M.S.; Khan, F.; Taekeun, W. Application of Internet of Things and Sensors in Healthcare. *Sensors* **2022** , 22 , 5738.
5. Berolo, S.; Wells, R.P.; Amick, B.C., 3rd. Musculoskeletal symptoms among mobile hand-held device users and their relationship to device use: A preliminary study in a Canadian university population. *Appl. Ergon.* **2011** , 42 , 371–378
6. Bragazzi, N.L.; Re, T.S.; Zerbetto, R. The relationship between nomophobia and maladaptive coping styles in a sample of Italian young adults: Insights and implications from a cross-sectional study. *JMIR Ment. Health* **2019** , 6 , e13154.]
7. Olczak, A.; Truszczyńska-Baszak, A.; Stępień, A. The Use of Armeo® Spring Device to Assess the Effect of Trunk Stabilization Exercises on the Functional Capabilities of the Upper Limb—An Observational Study of Patients after Stroke. *Sensors* **2022** , 22 , 4336.
8. Lai, CH; Sung, W. H.; Chiang, S.L.; Lu, L.H.; Lin, CH; Tung, Y. C.; Lin, CH Bimanual coordination deficits in hands following stroke and their relationship with motor and functional performance. *J. Neuroeng. Rehabil.* **2019** , 16 , 101.
9. Zhang, Q.-H.; Zheng, D.; Liu, S.-Q.; Zeng, C.-Y.; Xu, Y.-F.; Li, X.-Q. Therapeutic effect of Peto method on the recovery of the motor function in children with cerebral palsy. *Chin. J. Clin. Rehabil.* **2004** , 8 , 2902–2903. [[Google Scholar](#)]
10. Pérez-de la Cruz, S. Use of Robotic Devices for Gait Training in Patients Diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis: Current State of the Art. *Sensors* **2022** , 22 , 2580. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

AICON

**2024 International Conference on Artificial intelligence: from theory to practice,
17-18 september 2024, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan**

11. Zaralieva, A.; Georgiev, G.P.; Karabinov, V.; Iliev, A.; Aleksiev, A. Physical Therapy and Rehabilitation Approaches in Patients with Carpal Tunnel Syndrome. *Cureus* **2020** , 12 , e7171. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Troev, T.; Zaralieva, A.; Lutskanova, S. The Application of Physical Medicine in Medical Practice. In Proceedings of the Second International Scientific and Practical Conference: Nature, Forest, Society. Nature and Habitats, Human Activity and Hunting, Alternative and Hunting Tourism. Problems and Interconnection, Belarus; 2014. [[Google Scholar](#)]